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EDITORIAL: FROM THE CZECH LANDS TO STOCKHOLM

By VÁCLAV PAVLÍK

Nobel Prizes are often read as markers of national achievement, but in Central Europe, such labels rarely fit neatly. Borders have often shifted, and many careers unfolded across several countries. The connection between Nobel laureates and the Czech Lands is, therefore, best understood not as a simple list of national representatives but as a set of scientific and cultural trajectories that passed through Prague, Brno, Plzeň, and beyond.

In the natural sciences, the clearest and most direct case is Jaroslav Heyrovský. He was awarded the Nobel Prize in Chemistry in 1959 for the discovery and development

Jaroslav Heyrovský (credit: Archive of J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry, Czech Academy of Sciences)

of polarography, a new analytical method that had a lasting impact on electrochemistry. The prize came after a long sequence of nominations: Heyrovský was nominated eighteen times in total – i.e. fourteen times in chemistry between 1934 and 1959, once in physics, and three times in physiology and medicine. In 1958, his nomination was supported by previous Nobel laureates, including Archer John Porter Martin and Chandrasekhara Venkata Raman. Heyrovský delivered his Nobel lecture on the directions of polarographic research, reflecting a body of work that had been developed largely within Czechoslovakia and its scientific institutions.

In literature, the Czech connection is represented by Jaroslav Seifert, who was awarded the Nobel Prize in 1984. Seifert was not only a poet of international standing but also a central figure in modern Czech literature. His work shaped the Czech poetic language across much of the twentieth century, from early avant-garde movements through later, more personal and reflective writing. The Nobel Committee cited his poetry for its freshness, sensuality, and humane quality. Seifert's contribution is inseparable from Czech literature itself.

Other Nobel laureates are connected to the Czech lands primarily by birth or early education, rather than by nationality at the time of the award. Carl and Gerty Cori (Nobel laureates in Physiology or Medicine in 1947) were both born in Prague, but received their prize as American scientists. Peter Grünberg (co-recipient of the 2007 Nobel Prize in Physics for the discovery of giant magnetoresistance) was born in Plzeň, yet carried out his work within the German research system. Similarly, Bertha von Suttner, born in Prague and awarded the Nobel Peace Prize in 1905, belonged to the political and cultural world of the Austro-Hungarian Empire.

Jaroslav Seifert (credit: Hana Hamplová, 1981)

Together, these achievements illustrate how scientific and cultural work associated with the Czech Lands often crossed borders. While some of them were made locally and recognised as such, others emerged from early influences that were later expressed elsewhere.

INCREDIBLE BRNO

By PAVEL GABZDYL

I am a trained geologist and work as a science communicator specialising in astronomy. Whether I like it or not, this forces me to look at the world around me through different eyes than ordinary mortals. It may sound strange, but I like to imagine the surrounding landscape on a geological and astronomical scale. So, while historians passionately debate civilisations thousands of years old, for me, the past only becomes interesting when it goes back millions (or better yet, billions) of years.

The most prominent landmark in Brno – the St. Peter and Paul Cathedral – stands on a hill formed from some of the oldest volcanic rock in the Czech Republic. Incidentally, an image of this landmark also appears on the face of the Czech ten-crown coin. (credit: [Pavel Gabzdyl](#))

I tried to look at the city of Brno, where I have lived and worked for 25 years, from this perspective. I did so through a successful performance for the Brno Planetarium (in 2011), followed by a book [1] and finally a photographic project of the same name (both in 2016), which resulted in collaboration with the city of Brno and other organisations and artists. In this short text, I would like to focus directly on the oldest story. The story that stands at the very origins of our city. Or rather, the land on which it stands.

Seven hundred million years ago, the solid continental base of present-day Brno was located roughly where giant glaciers now slide into the waters of the Southern Ocean. However, this does not mean that the original Brno landscape was covered by an ice sheet at that time. Quite the contrary! It was hot here. Geologists have a lot of evidence that at least part of that ancient microcontinent was formed by a belt of active volcanoes. Like the area of present-day Japan or Indonesia, two oceanic plates collided here, one sliding under the other. The result was the formation of a series of undersea volcanoes that created a special type of lava that resembled pillows or loaves of bread after solidifying. That is why they are called pillow lavas.

Some of the oldest rocks in Brno really do resemble the lava that flows today on the ocean floor near mid-ocean ridges. The pillow shape of this lava is created when two

elements meet – fire and water. When hot lava pours out on the ocean floor, its surface quickly vitrifies upon contact with cold water and forms a “pillow”. In the case of the Brno “pillows”, however, we should keep in mind that these are rocks that have been mercilessly transformed, crushed, and deformed many times during dramatic folding processes, so that virtually nothing remains of their original shapes.

Much more than the rocks themselves, however, I would like to draw your attention to the remains of ancient undersea volcanoes, which today form a series of striking peaks right in the downtown of the city. For example, St. Peter and Paul Cathedral is located on one of them. The Špilberk castle fortress also stands on a hill whose foundations were created by ancient volcanic activity. However, Špilberk Hill has been covered with park greenery since the mid-19th century, so its rough rocky base can only be seen in a few places.

But that’s not the end of Brno’s story! Brno is an incredible city. About half a billion years ago, it had its own very small continent, with sharks larger than today’s humans once roaming the shallow sea, and the rock under Petrov was formed by underwater volcanoes. We know that trilobites, dinosaurs, and sabre-toothed tigers lived here. Huge comets appeared in the Brno sky, and the sun turned black many times during the day. The construction of the metro and the first European skyscraper began in Brno long ago. Believe it or not, these stories are inscribed in the streets, hills, and ordinary stones of Brno. All you have to do is look around you. Through the eyes of a geologist or astronomer.

[1] P. Gabzdyl. *Neuvěřitelné Brno*. CPress, 2016.

Throughout its history, Brno must have witnessed many breathtaking celestial displays. The photo shows the evening alignment of the Moon, Venus, and Jupiter on June 20, 2015, taken from the top of *Bílá hora*. (credit: [Pavel Gabzdyl](#))

Left photo: Michal Zajačec (IAUS405 SOC Chair), Jan Zouhar (Vice-Dean for Quality and Personnel Development at the Faculty of AgriSciences of Mendel University in Brno), Andrea Ghez (Nobel Prize Laureate), Tomáš Ondro (IAUS405 LOC). Right photo: A. Ghez discussing the Galactic Centre and the ‘paradox of youth’ during the opening lecture of IAU Symposium 405. (credit: Lea Szakszonová)

ANDREA GHEZ ON MEASURING THE GALACTIC CENTER

By VÁCLAV PAVLÍK

Andrea Ghez received the 2020 Nobel Prize in Physics for the discovery of a supermassive compact object at the centre of the Milky Way. At IAU Symposium 405, where she delivered the opening lecture, we spoke about black holes and about the elegance and mysteries of physics.

VP: I would like to begin this interview by gifting you my recent children’s book on astronomy, where the central character is a growing supermassive black hole.

AG: Oh, thank you. I love it!

VP: On that note, what do you think is the most important thing children should know about black holes?

AG: They are the coolest objects in the universe! They are cool because we do not know what they are. And that tells you that they must be really interesting to look at.

VP: Black holes are often seen as cosmic monsters. What is the biggest misconception people have about them?

AG: Yes, they are seen as vacuum cleaners, which is totally wrong. . . They are not going to suck everything up. They do accrete,

they do gobble stuff up, but we are safe, and even the stars that are very close are pretty safe as well.

Now, I am realizing that thanks to seeing your book in front of me, I am probably answering on the kids’ level and not the Conference Newsletter level. (laughs)

VP: That is completely fine. I wanted to start our conversation a bit lighter before we get to some deeper questions.

Black holes are remarkably simple mathematical objects; they famously have no hair. Do you think their mathematical simplicity hints at something fundamental about the structure of our universe?

AG: That is such an interesting question because we do not really know what a black hole is. So, while on the one hand we can say it is very simple and that we can describe it with three parameters, or characteristics, we do not ultimately have the physics to explain them. It certainly hints at the fact that they represent something fundamental that we do not understand yet.

VP: Do you think the whole universe ought to be described by the simplest equations possible?

AG: As physicists, we like the concept of Occam’s razor, that the simplest explanation is the best one. But I do not really know where that leads us. At least in terms of black holes, they are really a conundrum, although one

would hope they are simple. . . I see how one might posit that whatever physics describes a black hole also describes, for instance, where the universe originated, or another equally perplexing conundrum that we have on that scale. But there is no certainty in that.

VP: Focusing on the Nobel Prize, your observations of stars orbiting Sgr A* gave us some of the strongest evidence for a supermassive compact object at the center of the Milky Way. Was there a particular moment when you realised the evidence had become undeniable?

AG: Once we got to the scale of orbits. The whole project has been a series of surprises, but in terms of the best that we could possibly do was around 2003, when the stars went through the closest approach, and we had enough of the orbit to really understand its shape.

VP: Astronomy often requires decades of patience before a breakthrough arrives. How did these long timescales shape you as a scientist?

AG: I did not know that the time scales were going to be long – I think that was very fortunate! I do not think I would have been audacious enough to envision something this long because this all started in my first year as a faculty member. At that point, you are not thinking about long-term projects. Moreover, I was working in a totally different field,

so this was a new project – high-risk, high-reward – and we only envisioned it for three years. But then it became a five-year project, then a ten-year project, and now a thirty-year project. Still, with each step, it became clear where the next step was.

Fortunately, there was short-term science that could be pulled out from the same data set. The complementarity between the short- and longer-term projects has been really helpful in terms of our engagement with the project.

VP: Nowadays, in an era of artificial intelligence, automated surveys, and enormous datasets, what remains uniquely human in observational astronomy?

AG: I think it's still the creative case, making jumps, and linking things together. Who knows what AI is going to be capable of in the future, but I think it's the creativity piece that makes science human today.

VP: Finally, after spending so much of your career studying the center of our Galaxy,

Presenting Andrea Ghez with the children's astronomy book *The ever-hungry black hole* [1] prior to the interview. (credit: David Kománek)

what mystery about black holes still keeps you awake at night?

AG: Hm. . . Sometimes, it is the thought of whether you made a mistake. Because what makes the project interesting is that we

keep finding things that do not make sense. And when things do not make sense, it is either a mistake or a discovery.

VP: How do you recognise a mistake and distinguish it from a discovery?

AG: It is hard because if something does not make sense, the natural tendency is to say 'oh, it went wrong'. But you do not want to cover up something that is actually correct and unanticipated. In this experiment, one of the most unanticipated result was the discovery of the young stars. It is also really fun when these unexpected discoveries motivate theoretical work from many different corners – and we have seen that again and again. It is exciting and gratifying to be able to add knowledge to our knowledge base.

To me, the most interesting thing as a scientist is when you are trying to figure out the unknown, because there is no solution book. ■

[1] V. Pavlík. *The ever-hungry black hole*. Prague, CZ: Aventinum, 2026.

BRNO BECOMES THE “CENTER OF THE MILKY WAY”

By VLADIMÍR KARAS

The International Astronomical Union (IAU), established in 1919, has had the Czech Republic (formerly Czechoslovakia) as an active member since 1922. IAU's activities have included organizing General Assemblies, international symposia, workshops, and scientific events for the general public.

In the past century, as well as the current one, IAU-sponsored conferences have attracted many participants from around the globe to the country. The XIIIth IAU General Assembly in 1967 was followed by the XXVIth IAU General Assembly in 2006. Both took place in the capital city of Prague and featured topics of utmost importance to astronomers of those eras. Some of these discussions have had a significant impact lasting to date.

Two decades ago, Professor Reinhard Genzel delivered an Invited Discourse and Public Lecture describing the tremendous progress in high-resolution techniques to study the environs of Sagittarius A* super-massive black hole. The Galactic Center

has been established as the place of the best astrophysical evidence for the existence of black holes, which have long been only postulated, and also an ideal laboratory for studying the physics in the immediate neighborhood of such an object. Measurements employing adaptive optics imaging on 10m telescopes allowed determining the three-dimensional orbits of stars within ten light hours of the compact radio source at the center of the Milky Way! Among other topics discussed during the IAU Symposium #238, titled “Black Holes – from Stars to Galaxies across the Range of Masses”, were ways of weighing black holes with flares and spots, which were discussed (at that time Sgr A* was believed to be 3.7 million M_{\odot}).

In an interview published during the 2006 IAU General Assembly in Prague [1], Reinhard Genzel described the Galactic Centre as follows:

“Evidence has been accumulating for several decades that quasars, the most luminous objects in the Universe, are powered by accretion of matter onto massive black holes. Recent observations [. . .] prove the existence of such a massive black

hole in the centre of our Milky Way, beyond any reasonable doubt.”

— Reinhard Genzel

The interview also captured several unresolved questions that still resonate today. Genzel discussed the surprising presence of young stars close to Sgr A*, where tidal forces should make star formation difficult, and speculated that dense gas clouds falling into the Galactic Centre might temporarily overcome these conditions. He also reflected on the broader role of supermassive black holes in galaxy evolution, suggesting that many galaxies host “sleeping” black holes that were once far more active and influential in shaping their surroundings.

Today's *Traversing the Galactic Center in Space and Time* is the first IAU Symposium that takes place directly in Brno – a lively university town in the region of Moravia. We are delighted to welcome the Galactic Center community and to offer an exciting scientific and social program, thanks to support from the IAU and the combined enthusiasm of the SOC and LOC. ■

[1] J. Olivová. *Astropis S* (2006). <https://www.astropis.cz>, 32–33.